

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL
COMMITMENT BETWEEN MOBBING AND TURNOVER
INTENTION: AN APPLICATION ON PHYSICAL
EDUCATION AND SPORTS TEACHERS**

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to examine the mediating effect of organizational commitment between mobbing and turnover intention, on physical education and sports teachers. The study included 117 physical education and sports teachers. As the measurement tool, the mobbing scale developed by Yildiz (2019), the organizational commitment scale developed by Allen and Meyer (1990), and the turnover intention scale developed by Landau and Hammer (1986) were used. As a result of the analysis, while mobbing affects organizational commitment significantly and negatively, it has affected turnover intention significantly and positively. It was also observed that organizational commitment has a partial mediating effect between mobbing and turnover intention.

Keywords: mobbing, organizational commitment, turnover intention, physical education and sports teacher

1. Introduction

Mobbing, organizational commitment, and turnover intention are among the topics studied in various fields in the literature. In recent years, these issues have started to be studied especially in the field of sports (Güllü, 2019; Güllü and Yildiz, 2019). Although

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there are researches in every profession, including teachers (Sağlam, 2008), it can be said that new studies have been started on physical education and sports teachers.

Mobbing is a phenomenon that every employee can come face to face (Escartin et al., 2009). Leymann (1996) was the first scientist to scientifically study mobbing in the organizational environment. Leymann defined mobbing as “... a social interaction through which one individual (seldom more) is attacked by one or more (seldom more than four) individuals almost on a daily basis and for periods of many months, bringing the person into an almost helpless with potentially high risk of expulsion.” (p. 168).

Leymann has gathered the mobbing behaviors under five main headings: “communication, social relations, reputation, profession, and health” of the person. The person applying the mobbing can exhibit negative behaviors by using one or more of these titles (Zapf, Knorz, and Kulla, 1996). Mobbing is a phenomenon that disrupts the peace in the work environment and reduces the motivation of the employees (Psunder, 2015). Employees who are exposed to mobbing experience serious psychological problems, as a result, it can cause the employee’s turnover intentions (Yildiz, 2018).

Organizational commitment is an important issue that ensures employees’ loyalty to their organizations. This concept is defined as the contribution of employees to organizational activity and productivity by psychologically internalizing their organizations (Reichers, 1985). Allen and Meyer (1990) divide organizational commitment into three dimensions: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Affective commitment means being attached to the organization of the employee, continuance commitment, employee continuing compulsory to work in the organization, normative commitment means that the employee continues to work in the organization as a liability. Organizational commitment is an important factor that provides organizational effectiveness (Angle and Perry, 1981). Although determinants of organizational commitment are factors such as internal marketing (Yildiz, 2011a), job satisfaction (Bateman and Strasser, 1984; Yildiz, 2011a), and rewarding (Mottaz, 1988), there are also negative factors such as mobbing (Yüksel and Tunçsiper, 2011).

The turnover intention is a concept related to whether or not an employee remains at work. Ali (2008) defined turnover intention as the intention of employees to quit their organization. Since the turnover intention is a situation that can put organizations’ production processes in trouble, it is a factor that directly affects organizational performance (Lai and Chen, 2012).

It has been observed in the literature that mobbing (Çelebi and Kaya, 2014), organizational commitment (Güllü and Yenel, 2015), and turnover intention (Uzun, 2018) are studied on teachers. When the researches conducted in educational organizations are examined, it is seen that the majority of teachers are exposed to at least one of mobbing behaviors (Daşçı ve Cemaloğlu, 2015). We think that mobbing’s behavior will decrease teachers’ organizational commitment and increase their turnover intentions. Relationships between these three variables have not been studied on physical education teachers. Therefore, the results of this study will contribute to the literature.

The primary purpose of this study is to examine the relationships between mobbing, organizational commitment, and turnover intention. The secondary aim is to determine the mediating effect of organizational commitment between mobbing and turnover intention.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model and Hypothesis

The model of this research is presented in Figure 1. This model shows the cause and effect relationship between the variables, that is, the effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable, the independent variable on the dependent variable and the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable. Accordingly, the following hypotheses have been developed:

H₁: Mobbing has a significant and negative effect on physical education and sports teachers' organizational commitment.

H₂: Mobbing has a significant and positive effect on physical education and sports teachers' turnover intention.

H₃: Organizational commitment has a mediating effect between mobbing and turnover intention.

Figure 1: Relationships among mobbing, organizational commitment, and turnover intention

2.2. Data Collection Tools

In this study, the mobbing scale developed by Yildiz (2019), to measure the teachers' mobbing perceptions was used. This scale is two-dimensional (vertical mobbing, and vertical/horizontal mobbing) and consists of 10 items. The alpha coefficient of vertical mobbing is 0.75, and vertical/horizontal mobbing is 0.92. In order to measure the teachers' organizational commitment perceptions, the organizational commitment scale developed by Allen and Meyer (1990) was used. This scale is three-dimensional (affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment) and consists of 18 items. The alpha coefficient of affective commitment is 0.86, continuance commitment is 0.82, and normative commitment is 0.73. To measure teachers' turnover intentions, the turnover intention scale developed by Landau and Hammer (1986). This scale is one-dimensional and consists of 3 items. The alpha coefficient of the scale is 0.88.

Scale items were measured on a five-point Likert type scale (1=never; 5=every time) for the mobbing scale. The items of the organizational commitment and the

turnover intention scales were measured on a five-point Likert type scale (1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree).

2.3. Sample Size

In this study, sampling was chosen as a simple random sampling research method since the researchers' time, resources and workforce are limited. By using electronic communication tools, 160 physical education and sports teachers were reached with a message describing the purpose of the research. The number of scales obtained after 3 weeks was found to be 117.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and hierarchical regression analysis were applied for the data, in this study. Reliability of the scales was determined by Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

3. Findings

3.1. Demographic Properties of Participants

According to demographic characteristics, 60.7% of the teachers are male, 39.3% are female, 70.9% are married, and 29.1% are single. 21.4% of them have a master's degree. Teachers with ages between 46 and 55 make up the most in the age category. Those aged 21 and over constitute the highest percentage.

Table 1: Demographic Properties

Variables		f	%
Gender	Male	71	60.7
	Female	46	39.3
Marital status	Married	83	70.9
	Single	34	29.1
Age	25 and younger	4	3.4
	26-35	29	24.8
	36-45	40	34.2
	46-55	41	35.0
Educational status	56 and older	3	2.6
	Undergraduate	92	78.6
	Master's	25	21.4
Working life	1-5 years	9	7.7
	6-10 years	21	17.9
	11-15 years	19	16.2
	16-20 years	20	17.1
	21 years and higher	48	41.0

3.2. Reliability Analysis of the Scales

According to the results of the reliability analysis, the reliability coefficient of the mobbing scale is 0.938, the reliability coefficient of the organizational commitment scale is 0.851, and the reliability coefficient of the turnover intention is 0.881. These results show that the reliability of all scales is quite high.

3.3. Correlation Analysis

According to the correlation analysis, there is a significant and negative relationship between mobbing and organizational commitment ($r=-.183$). There is a significant and positive relationship between mobbing and turnover intention ($r=.536$). There is a significant and negative relationship between organizational commitment and turnover intention ($r=-.411$). Of the demographic characteristics, only the educational status has a significant relationship with turnover intention.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Gender	1						
2. Marital status	.256**	1					
3. Age	-.114	-.329**	1				
4. Educational status	-.078	-.058	.111	1			
5. Working life	-.183*	-.377**	.813**	.054	1		
6. Mobbing	-.047	.059	-.038	.092	-.008	1	
7. Organizational commitment	-.132	-.201*	.107	-.152	.089	-.183*	1
8. Turnover intention	.022	.063	-.025	.291**	-.015	.536**	-.411**

** $p<0.01$, * $p<0.05$

3.4. Hierarchical Regression Analysis

According to hierarchical regression analysis results, mobbing affects organizational commitment significantly and negatively in Model 1 ($\beta=-.183$). According to this result, hypothesis 1 was accepted (Table 3).

Table 3: The Effect of Mobbing on Organizational Commitment

Model 1				
Independent variable	Organizational Commitment			
	Beta	F	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Mobbing	-.183**	3.966	.033	.025

* $p<0.01$, ** $p<0.05$

In Model 2, mobbing affects the turnover intention significantly and positively ($\beta=.536$). According to this result, hypothesis 2 was accepted (Table 4).

Table 4: The Effect of Mobbing on Turnover Intention

Model 2				
Independent variable	Turnover Intention			
	Beta	F	R²	Adjusted R²
Mobbing	.536*	46.345	.287	.281

* p<0.01, **p<0.05

The beta value of mobbing, which was 0.536 in Model 2, dropped to 0.477 in Model 2 and Model 3. This drop in beta value indicates that organizational commitment has a partial mediating effect between mobbing and turnover intention (Table 5). According to this result, hypothesis 3 was accepted.

Table 5: The Mediating Effect of Organizational Commitment between Mobbing and Turnover Intention

Model 3				
Independent variable	Turnover Intention			
	Beta	F	R²	Adjusted R²
Mobbing	.477*	36.219	.389	.378
Organizational Commitment	-.324*			

* p<0.01, **p<0.05

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study showed that mobbing affects teachers' organizational commitment significantly and negatively, and their turnover intentions significantly and positively. Organizational commitment also negatively affected teachers' turnover intentions. According to these results, it can be said that mobbing behaviors have an effect that decreases teachers' organizational commitment and increases their turnover intentions. Teachers whose organizational commitment decreases have more intention to leave the job. According to another result of this study, organizational commitment has a partial mediating effect between mobbing and turnover intention. That is, the turnover intention can be seen in teachers who are exposed to mobbing behavior, and the turnover intention in teachers whose organizational commitment is reduced.

It is seen in the literature that there are many factors that affect teachers' turnover intentions. Job motivation (Houkes et al., 2003), stress (Liu and Onwuegbuzie, 2012), and burnout (Goddard and Goddard, 2006) are examples. Mobbing and organizational commitment are also other important factors that affect teachers' turnover intentions. According to Gökaslan's (2018) study, teachers' turnover intentions are decreasing as their organizational commitment increases. In his study on teachers, Okubanjo (2014) found that organizational commitment significantly and negatively affects their turnover intentions. Ünal (2019) found that mobbing behaviors increase teachers' turnover intentions.

As can be seen above, both mobbing and organizational commitment are among the important factors affecting teachers' turnover intentions. In the literature, no studies

investigating the relationship between these three variables on teachers have been encountered. Therefore, the results of our study will contribute to the literature.

In order to see a positive climate and positive behaviors in schools, administrators must first show effective leadership by increasing the relationship quality with teachers (Yildiz, 2011b). When teachers are shown effective leadership by school administrations, negative behaviors such as mobbing will not be observed in schools; on the contrary, extra-role behaviors will be created that will contribute to the performance of the school, such as organizational commitment feelings and organizational citizenship behavior. As a strategy to prevent mobbing, positive relationships between employees should be encouraged, a climate should be created to ensure harmony among teachers, and vocational training on ethics should be provided (Psunder, 2011). Thus, negative behaviors will not emerge in schools, and teachers' organizational commitment will increase, and their turnover intention will decrease.

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